

ALTERNATIVES TO PUNISHMENT PAROLE AND OPEN PRISON

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ABSTRACT

Punishment from the past have been a source of justice for the incarceration of the prisoner made the victim feel satisfied for the sins the prisoner committed he has to pay for it. Slowly with change in time we have come across many committees who have devised certain methods which can serve both as incarceration and reformatory at the same time. In the past we only used to look at it from the angle of retribution that is to say the offender has to suffer for his misdeeds. But now with the evolution of certain methods such as Parole and Open Prisons which are serving as guiding light towards their reformation. For in several countries such as USA, India are coming up with ways to employ them in certain activities for their enhancement and upgradation of their skill sets. Parole being one of it wherein certain period is given to the prisoner to meet with his family and be connected and sensitive towards it. This also serves as the period for him to breathe fresh air and come in contact with society. Open Prison has been the recent development which is serving as one of the process which makes the prisoner engaged in certain set of works and as a result of which disciplined and ready for the employment after getting out of the Prison. In the meantime it also makes him aware about the surroundings and a change in the mind of him which can further reform him for future endeavors.

Introduction

Incarceration is another form of punishment. Punishment one of the purposes being reform and rehabilitation of the offender. Our Constitution has the inclusion of “law and order” and “prison” in the List Of State as per the Schedule Seven. Central Government has a part to play¹.

Mahatma Gandhi in one of his sayings has stated that Jail must act as a hospital for care and treatment of person who have committed crime as a result of mind being diseased with such thoughts.

Manu states that through Punishment fear there exists check as it is difficult to find a man who sticks to the virtuous path².

Also as per Manu the purpose of Penalty imposition is to provide protection to the sufferer by acting as an deterrent effect, and also it remains awake causing the offender to never escape from its clutches.

Certain philosophers from various times had their say on definition regarding Punishment. As per them certain conditions that can be attributed are as under:

- a. Authority imposes it.
- b. Offender goes through loss.
- c. Offence gave rise to it.
- d. Responsibility for such offence somewhat rests on such human as well to whom such injury caused.

HLA Hart³ one of the renowned jurist defined Punishment as instrument which:

- I. Consequence is involving pain.
- II. Legal rules violation by committing an offence.
- III. Actual or supposed offender covered under it.
- IV. Administered intentionally by human beings.

¹ Nishant Krishna Adhikari, “Prison and Prison Reforms in India,” 4(4) *International Journal of Law Management & Humanities*, 2161, 2161-2168 (2021)

² Shyam Prakash Pandey, “Kinds of Punishment under Indian Penal Code : A Critical Evaluation and Need for Reform,” 4(1) *International Journal of Law Management & Humanities*, 1699-1700, 1699-1716 (2021)

³ HLA Hart, “Punishment And Responsibility: Essays In The Philosophy”, (2nd Edition, New Oxford University Press, 1968)

V. Legal system administration.

Parole

The word Parole has its origin from French word 'Parole' meaning "word of honour". It was mostly associated with prisoners who kept their words upon their release

In the words of Dr.Sutherland releasing a prisoner or being released from an institution which is reformatory or penal where maximum period of his punishment has been served and with certain restrictions on behaving in a good way and being under the institution guidance and custody of that particular state till his discharge⁴.

Origin

Samuel Howe⁵ was the early propounder of the word 'Parole'.

USA

Origin

The prisoners were handed over to employers on condition that they will be under the supervision of employer and if they do not behave properly will be sent back⁶. Many societies were formed for Prison Aid by the end of 1800s. The first to adopt the system of parole was in the State of New York of Reformatory Elmira in 1869⁷.

Developments

The Reforms Act with regard to Parole of 1977, provided with a system which is uniform and so that it can do away with the evil effects in sentencing inequality and also on the psychology of prisoner⁸.

The Parole Board in U.S⁹. is composed of sociologists, penologists and psychologists also lawyers and is a gamut for determining the time as to release of prisoner on parole.

⁴ Sutherland & Cressey : Principles of Criminology 556 (11th Ed. 2013)

⁵ Mitchel P. Roth Prisons and Prison Systems: A Global Encyclopedia (Greenwood Publishing Group, Westport 2006),130

⁶ Barnes and Teeters , "New Horizons in Criminology" 423 (3rd Edn)

⁷ Prisoners Rehabilitation Act 1965 USA

⁸ Parole Reforms Act 1977 USA

⁹ N V Paranjape, "Criminology & Penology" 592

Certain considerations to be taken into mind such as:

- I. After his departure from prison a better environment is waiting for her
- II. Also there is employment opportunities available for him.

After their discharge they are put under surveillance of Officers concerned with Parole who see to it that they conform to the conditions and also they guide in job availability and their restoration back to the society.

India

Origin

The Parole history can be discussed from the Supreme Court case of *Smt.Poonam Lata v . Wadhwan*¹⁰ in which it is stated that it is a concept that has taken wings from law of military and involves prisoners from war their release or on return promise. As a result of which all sentences of fixed term involving 18 months above imprisonment subjected to license release, which pertains to release on completion of one third of sentence.

Developments

Parole System in the Indian subcontinent is governed by rules under the Prison Act,1894¹¹ and Prisoners Act,1900¹². Every State has its own rules regarding it with some slight variation.

The laws enacted under the Prison Act of 1894 and the Prisoners Act of 1900 govern the award of parole in India. The Prisons (Bombay Furlough and Parole) Rules, 1959, were issued under Section 59(5) of the Prisons Act, 1984, which gives the government the right to make rules. The prisoner does not have to serve the remainder of his or her term on furlough, as is the case with parole.

In the case of *Budhi v. State of Rajasthan*¹³, serves three purposes:

- a. It acts as motivation for the offenders and aids them in making changes for their benefit.
- b. Ensures that the ties of family remain intact and there is no disruption.
- c. Lastly makes them capable to face the society as a whole.

¹⁰ AIR 1987 SC 1383

¹¹ The Prisons Act, 1894

¹² The Prisoners Act,1900

¹³ AIR 2006

In the case of *Charanjit Lal v. State of Delhi*¹⁴ the following observations were taken into account

1. The four goals of a State are to reform, retribute, deter, and prevent the offender.
2. In order to maintain their relations with their family the life convict be given periodic release.
3. Also they be provided opportunity to breath fresh air based on their conduct.
4. Redemption and Rehabilitation must be given due consideration.

Eligibility

According to the Guidelines of 2010 Parole/Furlough¹⁵, to be eligible for parole:

- a. A convict must have served at least one year in jail, excluding any time spent in remission.
- b. The prisoner's behaviour had to be uniformly good.
- c. The criminal should not have committed any crimes during the period of parole if it was granted previously.
- d. The convict should not have broken any of the terms and restrictions of his or her previous release.
- e. A minimum of six months should have passed since the previous parole was terminated.

Cases

In *Suresh Chandra v. State of Gujarat*¹⁶ it was stated that Parole is regarded as an innovation in penology and has resulted in reforming the offender thereby stopping him from doing the same offence again .

In *Dharambir And Another v. State Of U.P*¹⁷ It was directed by the Apex Court that such prisoners who are serving long time in jail be given two weeks once a year throughout their period of imprisonment.

¹⁴ AIR 1985

¹⁵ Parole / Furlough Guidelines 2010

¹⁶ AIR 1976 SC 2462

¹⁷ AIR 1979

Open Prisons

Merriam Webster Dictionary defines open prison in which freedom is provided to prisoners as opposed to normal prisons.

Section 2 clause a of The Rajasthan Prisoners Open Air Camp Rules¹⁸ define open jail as, place which is declared for the detention of prisoners to be Open Air Camp i.e. to say in simple words "Prisons without walls, bars and locks."

Origin

Sir Alexander Paterson¹⁹ laid emphasis on the establishment of Open prisons in England which later on went to other countries. This enthusiasm of him was being enumerated in the Prisons Rule 1964 rule 1 which states that the whole propaganda of rehabilitating and training him to make him be able to lead a good life should be the main goal.

Californian Prison Farms²⁰

During end of 2011, The Program relating to Conservation Camp contained 4100 prisoners who were adults in the fire camps which were forty two in the State in which 300 them were women . Most of them imprisoned are trained and certified to fight wildfires, a small group stay in camps and do institutional support jobs like clerks, janitors, etc.

For to be in fire camp prisoners must have 5 years of punishment left and also score below certain points to be considered that their security needed is medium or low. As opposed to common walled prison it has greenery and landscape which is attractive, and comparatively tasty and foods cooked by prisoners.

India

The First Committee of All India Jail of 1836 did not favour the prisoners employment for works in major public sites. In the year 1877 The Conference recommended prisoners employment for works of public development and was accepted²¹. The Committee of 1919-20²² headed by Alexander Cardew advocated for the humane treatment of offenders and also

¹⁸ The Rajasthan Prisoners Open Air Camp Rules, 1972

¹⁹ Rupert Cross, *"Punishment, Prison And The Public An Assessment of Penal Reform in Twentieth Century England by an Armchair Penologist"* (Stevens & Sons London 1971)

²⁰ Philip Goodman, "Another Second Chance": Rethinking Rehabilitation through the Lens of California's Prison Fire Camps," *59(4) University of California Press on behalf of the Society for the Study of Social Problems* (2012)

²¹ Report Of The Indian Jail Conference, Home Secretary Press (1877)

²² Report Of The Indian Jails Committee, Government Central Press,(1920)

employing them on farms concerning agriculture who were related to background of agriculturist. The Jail Committee of 1956-57²³ which was constituted after Technical Expert of U.N. Walter Reckless submitted Report concerning the administration of prison in India and the open jail for prisoners was recommended for rehabilitation of prisoners.

Cases

In *Dharambir And Another v. State Of U.P.*²⁴ The court took cognizance of the fact that the petitioners were in their twenties and so if the petitioners are languishing in jail for years it will have a larger impact on them as a result of which brings them into contact with those hardened offenders. Also the most important purpose of denying liberty for punishing an offender is to restore his self-esteem, dignity and so he becomes a useful person to the society.

So it was directed to the Prison Superintendent and Government of the State to engage them in useful work and if permission can be granted to open prisons and also they being agriculturists can be put to use as such and can also be made to learn some useful crafts so that they become citizens who are sensitive and not go back to the addition of criminals and also they can be paid wages in small amount so their mind can be fully healed.

In *Rama Murthy v. State Of Karnataka*²⁵ In this case petition in form of letter was addressed to Chief Justice India with regard to the issue as to wages not being paid to prisoners for their hardwork. The Bangalore District Judge was ordered to visit the Central Jail and file a report in which he stated certain recommendations such as:

- a. Maintenance of building properly by P.W.D.
- b. Sanitation to be improved.
- c. Increasing atleast 2 more Doctors in Jail specialising in particular field.
- d. Arrange regular visit for the homes visit of prisoners on periodic basis.

Court also took into account the role of open prisons representing principle of punishing individually for their again coming back to society in better state. Also some features of it being release on probation, prisoners home leave, wage system, parole release, vocational training, etc. Also what is stated in the book titled “Open Air Prisons” by B. Chandra Chapter

²³ Report Of The All India Jail Manual Committee (1957-59)

²⁴ AIR 1979

²⁵ AIR 1997

5 that the whole motive is to make them capable to earn livelihood by certain incentives such as training in fields of agriculture, horticulture, etc and some activities such as Games, Sports inculcating discipline.

Concluding Remarks

One of the open prison being of Sampurnanad²⁶ near Jaipur in Rajasthan and among 23 in the State and 46 in the country. From 2009 February to 2012 December there were 169 prisoners of which 15 were women and 154 were men. They built their houses and bills paid by them. Sarpanch is made after confirmation from them. 5-6 members to sort out the dispute. But they face certain hindrances such as facilities lacking for education, entertainment, medical, etc.

In the case of *Ahmed Ismail Sayyed v. State of Maharashtra*²⁷ It was stated by Krishna Iyer Justice of Bombay High Court that the person who is saint in front of us did have a past and the person who has committed sin does have a future. We just have to remove those retardness in the human by holistic approach.

The Open Jail²⁸ situated outside Central Jail Yerwada houses prisoners serving the sentence completed five years in the Central Jail. 150 inmates grow vegetables organic in nature, sent to Central Prison Yerwada and prison of women. Also from their family 4500 per month every inmate can receive and they are provided with daily basis opportunity to earn from the work which is divided amongst skilled, semi-skilled or no skill at all.

²⁶ Anupma Kaushik, Neetu Sharma, “3(1) *The International Journal of Political Science*,” Human Rights of Prisoners: A Case Study of Sampurnanad Open Prison, Sanganeer, Rajasthan, 7-9, (2017)

²⁷ AIR 2017

²⁸ Riya Ragini, “Report on Yerwada Prison,” 4(4) *International Journal of Law Management & Humanities*, 1494, 1493 – 1504 (2021)